

The Diaconate Election and Moral Behaviour in Acts 6:1-7: Political and Electoral Insights for National Integration in Nigeria

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Abstract

The management of human leadership has since time immemorial been a prime factor in all societies and groups. It is also a truism to say that, elections are mounted to enable states, nations and people to manage their material and human resources to the benefit of all citizens. This paper is a re-examination of biblical election found in Acts 6:1-7 and therefore a re-appraisal of it for national integration in Nigeria. Using the electoral political, comparative and ethical methods of analysis, this paper found out that, the elections of the deacons studied in the bible can provide the needed social, political and ethical behaviour to the management of elections in Nigeria which ultimately will bring about national integration, successful democratic practices and an enduring electoral framework for the management of elections in Nigeria. Suggestions including the constitutional, political, moral and attitudinal reforms by managers of elections and the electorate will certainly jettison the loopholes in our political life and bring about national integration in Nigeria.

Keywords: Elections, Democracy, Moral behaviour, National Integration.

Introduction

According to Professor Patrick Lewis in Jibrin, Jide, and Sako-John, “All Democracies confront the important tasks of broadening personal freedoms, encouraging genuine political competition; promoting the accountability of leaders, resolving conflicts; advancing a general rule of law; and building efficient and effective public institutions.”¹ The understanding from the submission above clearly shows that, elections are a necessary substratum on which democratic principles heavily rely namely; political behaviour, election morality vis-à-vis broadening personal freedoms genuine political competition, promoting accountability, resolving conflicts, setting a general rule and building efficient and effective public institutions to mention just a few. The imperativeness of elections to the nation, its inclusion in the constitution has long been settled in Nigeria. For instance, the qualification for elections and disqualification, the supervision of it and all other preliminary preparations are clearly spelt out in the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.²

To this effect, the present study sees the biblical diaconry elections as providing the needed parameters of effective election and the provision of general rules guiding public institutions in Nigeria besides the provision of virile political and moral codes for the conduct of elections for both the leaders, election managers and the masses. To do this, we shall follow this guideline to achieve this namely conceptual classification of terms, a consideration of the philosophy of elections, practice and importance of it, governance and democratic processes; religious elections in the Bible; the analysis of election of the deacons in Acts 6:1-7; matters arising from the election and lessons for Nigerians.

Conceptual Clarifications

Election(s)

Dibie defined election as the act of electing candidates to represent the people of a given country in the parliament, the executive and possibly into other areas of government as stipulated in the constitution of a particular country.³ Toluhi says that an election is usually brought about when people (the electorate in order to fill a position, collectively and voluntarily put their consent for the choice of a candidate into voting.⁴ Hounkpe, M. and Gueye, A.B. in Abiodun, defined election as “the most appropriate widespread mechanism for selecting their representative who will be responsible for governing on behalf of and for the people.⁵ From the few definitions captured above, some keywords describing the concept “election” can be pointed out. These include voting, appointing, choosing, selecting qualified candidates to represent the generality of people in a democracy. The people (masses) that choose, vote or select others must also be qualified by every legal framework provided by the constitution.

Democracy

The most simple and common definition of democracy is the one offered by one-time American President, Abraham Lincoln that, “Democracy is the government of the people, by the people for the people.”⁶ Democracy is therefore considered to be that form of government in which people, mostly indirectly, participate fully in constitution and running government with their clearly defined interests and objectives. It is also the constitution and running of government along the lines desired by the people through their representatives. Democracy has many attributes including good governance; rule of law; and it is tantamount to free and fair elections; freedom of speech, free assembly; free movement; and so on.

Democratic Challenges of Elections in Nigeria

Concerning the Nigerian political state, there have been a lot of electoral malpractices from leadership interference, to the abuse of electoral commissions, political party issues and generality of the people. Toluhi points to the lack of independence of electoral commissions in Nigeria that, “In Nigeria the recent performance of Electoral Commissions has left credibility of the commission to be doubted and questioned several times.”⁶ Independency of the electoral commission is not really independent. Some governments dictate the performance to suit its winning ways.

Another challenge of elections in Nigeria is that, the party in power uses the power of incumbency and makes sure other political parties do not enjoy the freedom of speech, assembly and movement necessary to voice their criticism of the government openly, and to bring alternative policies. This is against the democratic electoral ethics as pointed out by Kirkpatrick Jeane in Zuba that, in democratic elections that are competitive, opposition parties and candidates are allowed or must enjoy the freedom of speech, assembly and movement necessary to voice criticisms of government.⁷ Yet, opposition parties are often barred from the airwaves, has their rallies harassed or its newspapers censored. The media-state and private owned has often been directly involved in electoral politics with clear display preferences for certain candidates against such practice. Media bias and unfair coverage characterized the 2019 general election and, the most unfortunate aspect of it was the media involvement in facilitating hate campaigns during the process.⁸ There have been reports of how political parties and individuals have been tempting the commission with gifts and bribes in order to swing results and records to their favour. In much the same way, our judiciary have not been spared. Several cases of election tribunal reflect miscarriage of justice, when the political parties and politicians turn to the courts for illegal justice.⁹

Prominent and an ever increasing or re-current challenge has been the issue of violence. This comes in three faces namely pre-election violence; election violence and post-election violence. Several candidates from different political parties were attacked and sometimes killed by opponents. During elections and campaigns, substantive political issues are not addressed but trivial issues become the order of the day. Tesemchi Makar in Jibo, has shown that, “Showering abuses on each other... where the campaigns strained individual family

relationships”¹⁰ is the order of the day. During elections proper, political party supporters are attacked to disallow them from performing their civic duties on the basis of reducing the total number of votes coming from a political party not to have advantage over other candidates or party. This includes running down contestants and some personalities at election which according to Jibo has become a feature of Nigerian politics. In his words: “... in all ... a recourse is made to the personality of the candidate to win or lose votes in election.”¹¹

Going by the reports of Independent Electoral Commission, even the 2015 General Elections which were acclaimed to be the best in the country, there were reports of election day and post-election violence in some areas including Rivers, Taraba, Kogi, Plateau, Gombe, Enugu, Abi, Bauchi and Akwa-Ibom states.¹² Another aspect of this challenge is the partiality and connivance of the security agencies in stealing peoples mandate especially during the 2003, 2007 and 2011 general elections. In many polling stations across the country, they (security) were either used to scare away genuine voters by the ruling party or were seen thumb printing ballot papers in favour of some candidates at the expense of others.¹³

In all, considering the challenges of electoral processes in Nigeria, the writers agree with Ikponko in Katsina, and Akwaki to the effect that politics is a dirty game. He said, “Nigerian politics is faced with the grim prospect of being in the grips of antagonism and terror, unleashed and executed by those who breed the risk of party armies. The swords, knives which have become our voting cards, as spears and arrows have remained our thumbprints.”¹⁴

The Analysis of Election in Acts 6:1-7

Historically and chronologically, the election of the deacons took place before 46-48 AD. The reason being that, Paul’s first missionary journey took place around the period mentioned. The Early Church took off precisely on the day of the Pentecost after Peter’s speech. There were however only one hundred and twenty (120) disciples belonging to Jesus (Acts 1:15), added to the about three thousand souls that accepted the word of God one the day of the Pentecost (Act 2:41), and the number increased to over three thousand believers. Yet, the number kept increasing as noted in Acts 6:1, “Now in these days when the disciples (followers) were increasing in number...” This formed the quasi-Christian community where diverse Christian believers including Jews, Hellenists and others (Gentiles) became incorporated into the church of Christ. They pulled all their resources together (had all things in common). They also sold their belongings and goods and distributed the proceed to all, as any had need (Acts 2:43). They equally attended the temple together and broke bread in their homes, partook of food with glad and generous hearts to the effect of praising God, and having favour with all the people (Acts 2:44-47).

This somewhat Utopian community did not however last long as evident in the first verse of chapter six thus; the Hellenists murmured against Hebrews because their widows were neglected in the daily distribution. This eroded the personal rights of the Hellenist widows and so they had to complain. This is equally against the fundamental human rights of all humans. By the way, the Hellenist widows equally sold their possessions and brought their proceeds to the council of elders (Apostles). Why were they marginalized? Professor Lewis Patrick as cited by Nwabueze then points to how these problem can be solved and states: “the democratic problem in a plural society is to give all the various groups the opportunity to participate in decision making, since only thus can they feel that they are full members,... respected by their more numerous brethren and owing equal respect which holds them together.”¹⁶ The unbalanced leadership of those handling the distribution of food and other things needed to be corrected, because the Hebrews were in-effective.

To overcome this challenge, the twelve Apostles summoned the body of the disciples that, “It is not right we should give up preaching the word of God to serve tables” (6:2). These voluminous administration duties which accompanied the great growth of the Early Church, in Jerusalem,¹⁷ needed to apply the administrative and economic principle of “Division of Labour” and or “Delegated Legislation” as rightly opined by the Apostles.

The brethren were to do the choosing of seven men with the required qualifications namely, “men of good repute, full of the spirit and wisdom, whom we may appoint to this duty” (6:3) this was a right thing to do, that the entire congregation formed the electoral masses and to choose who will serve them. It must be remembered that the electoral masses included the Hebrews, the Hellenists and others. Nwabueze accepts this electoral

standard and states, “the entire country formed as it were a single constituency, in which the electors voted, not for individual candidates.”¹⁸

But again, the desired administrative and moral categories of those to be chosen were laid: “men of good repute” which shows that they were honest and truthful in their dealings prior to their choice. They were also “men full of spirit” that is men controlled and mindful of the direction of the Holy Spirit of God. This is the same thing as saying men in whose spirit there is no guile (Psalms 32:2). Also, “men of wisdom,” that is to be wise is to be prudent (Prov.16:21) and handle all matters justly and fairly, and behaving yourself in most modest forms of morality and social justice. The Apostles were very mindful of the fact that, “Representative democracy presupposes and rests on the capacity of people to choose the right representatives, that is to say, representatives imbued with a sense of the public good... requires civic virtues resting on morality-respect and obedience, fair play, tolerance, honesty, selflessness, self-restraints- what is often referred to as the democratic spirit, without these, no viable democracy for liberty can be established or be maintained.”¹⁹

It is said that, people who participate in the affairs of their nation or group without being coerced, provide such a government with legitimacy (support). The brethren willingly participated in the election (choice) of the seven deacons namely Stephen, Philip, Prochorus, Nicanor, Timon, Parmenas and Nicolaus which was followed by presentation to the Apostles and their inauguration-prayers and laying of hands upon them. This is a replication of what Moses did to Joshua (Num.27:18-23) that indicated designation for an office, work, or ministry.²⁰ Rightly, Nwabueze observes, that, democracy “must involve the local people in order to be able to grow and flourish.”²¹

The proper processes of election as followed by the Apostles and the disciples representing leaders and the led was successful namely the increasing of the word of God and the multiplication of the disciples in Jerusalem bringing a great many priests to the faith. This is an affirmation to the fact that, when countries, state or groups are well governed and the constitution followed to the letter, this becomes a “means” of organizing the government appropriate to an extension or multi-national state.”²² In another way it can be said that, “for the Christian, the practice of good work ethic is responsible for the well-being of the family, the progress of the nation and indeed the universe at large.”²³

The successful conduct of the election of the deacons is also a pointer to the fact that, the leaders and the led must be united in the pursuance of the policies of the state including election matters to be able to achieve integration and harmony. Temisan Ebijuwa corroborates this where he state that, “The obligation of the citizen to obey the laws of his government is congruent upon the government acting justly or ensuring through its laws that just relations prevail among its citizens-body.”²⁴ The in-balance in the daily distribution of resources was corrected by the choice of the seven who already had good and reputable character to do justice to the Hellenist Widows. After analysing the election of the deacon proper, it is good we look at political, electoral and moral substratum that will grow national integration in Nigeria.

The Political, Electoral and Moral Relevance of the Election of the Deacons to National Integration in Nigeria

Nwabueze noted that, government by the people is expected to be government for the people because the people embody all of the community’s wisdom, goodness, honesty, justice, its sense of right and wrong, in short all the civic virtues available in it, which should outweigh all its vices. This concern for their own good namely their safety, liberty, prosperity, well-being and happiness which is the same as the public good or the welfare of the community, government by the people cannot but be government for the people. Alexis de Toqueville agrees with Nwabueze and state that, the people, it is said, “Cannot have an interest opposed to their own advantage.”²⁵

Unfortunately, this actual working of popular representative government that is anchored on elections in Nigeria has proved all this to be loyal and ideal picture, quite removed from reality.²⁶ From the foregoing, it has been sufficiently shown that. “In recent times, one major problem that has beset Nigerian as a nation which has also affected various sectors of the nation is the appointment of public office holders into the helm of affairs of the nation.”²⁷ Ethnicity, (ethnocentric pride in one’s racial group and preference for their distinctive characteristics

of that group ... coupled with the thrust to discriminate against and exclude the out-group from full participation in the life of their community),²⁸ has divided Nigeria ever in elections. These racial/tribal sentiments as seen in the distribution of food in the early church have brought about murmurings in the Nigerian body polity. Akin Madu in Akwaki rightly captures that, “the ability to win and make others loose imposes on him contemptuous feelings for the others who needed to lose to give way for his victory.”²⁹ For those who have a tribalistic feeling and the subsequent demonstration of it during elections, should jettison such ideas and buy the idea of displayed by the leaders of the early church or Christians as demonstrated in Acts 6:1-7. John R. W. Stott in Clouse et al eloquently sums up the thrust of this call that, because of the unity of humankind we demand equal rights and equal respect for social minorities... we must seek to rid ourselves of any lingering racism and strive to make it a model of harmony between races, in which the multiracial dream comes true.”³⁰

Election matters are a collective process of the whole country, if ever the unity and integration of the country is to be achieved. For example, Goodluck Ebele Jonathan was able to provide the enabling environment during the 2015 General Elections. He equally did not interfere with the activities of the election under INEC Professor Attahiru Jega. The result was that he (Goodluck) was unseated, yet he chose to accept the results. The Apostles (Leaders) could have used their power to choose from the brethren members of the Deaconry, but they did not. This is a shining example for the country to copy. The bible says, “therefore, brethren, pick out from among you seven men.... (Act 6:3).

As long as the election of the deacons is concerned, it was a free and fair election because after the Apostles did not interfere with the choice, the brethren were left to do the picking. “And what they said pleased the multitude and they chose Stephen, Philip, Prochorus, Nicanor, Timon, Parmenas and Nicolaus” (Acts 6:5). We must learn from this the power of equality among the Apostles and the brethren (representing leaders and the led) that, “Liberty and democracy, if they are to take firm root and thrive, must have a foundation in certain shared sentiments that bind a society to respect human rights and to behave democratically.”³¹ There is little or no wonder therefore that Justice Felix Frank further remarked: “The ultimate foundation of a free society... is the binding tie of cohesive sentiment.”³²

One other important factor to the growth of democracy and good governance is the utmost faith in the Supreme Being (God). Lord Patrick Devlin in Nwabueze has made the point, that,

Those who believe in God and that He made man in His image in equal measure the knowledge of good and evil... in the heart and the understanding building there in each man the temple of the Holy Ghost. Those who do not believe in God must ask themselves what they mean when they say that they believe in democracy for if in this endowment men were not equal, it would be pernicious that in the government of any society they should have equal rights.³³

This Judeo-Christian worldview also finds relevance in the African cognitive orientation as echoed by Potholm Christian in Akwaki that in many African societies, leaders were afraid if they deviated from acceptable norms and of course many became targets irrespective of their political actions, but the most important assumption that even the lowest and the weakest commoner could call on enormous supernatural powers was a consistent potent check on the arbitrary use of power.³⁴ This Christian election would therefore serve as reminder and a return to free and fair elections as well as practice of true religion and democracy to keep us united and integrated as a nation.

The election of the seven into the administration of food and other resources was rooted on high moral standards namely: “...men of good repute full of spirit, and of wisdom, whom we may appoint to this duty.” (Acts 6:3) Here the attainment of goodness (fair play, tolerance, honesty, selflessness, self-restraint) can be identified, then a person whose work and work ethic is directed by the spirit of God. A man in whom the spirit of God is committed or invested has the authority of God such that what he does is in time with the will of the congregating of the people. But again, such a person should have wisdom. This in other words mean true knowledge and the education needed to govern a people. Plato also advocated for a philosopher King-must be educated in civic

matters before qualifying to rule the people. J.S Mill in Nwabueze corroborates that, “there is hardly any kind of intellectual work which so much needs to be done, not only by experienced and exercised minds, but by minds trained to the task through long and laborious study as the making of laws...”³⁵ If we are to overcome bringing into governance half-baked or illiterates who are selfish and ego-centric, we then must choose leaders with reputable characters as those in the Bible.

Consequently, when the people in a democratic dispensation choose their representatives based on the above moral categories, then, there is bound to be legitimacy to such a government. In Acts 6:5 the brethren (people) were pleased with their involvement in the consideration or qualification to choose and they happily did the election. After the election, those selected were presented or set before the Apostles and they prayed and laid hands upon them. Summarily therefore, the publicity, choosing and working according to the laws governing elections of the legal framework and taking of oath to the office(s) makes such election democratic among other things. This must be imbibed in Nigeria if the desired integration is to be achieved.

Conclusion

This work has shown that, there is an inextricable relationship between religious ideals and socio-political development precisely electoral matters. Historically, studies have also shown that, religious beliefs have through the ages been the main anchor of morality, providing the necessary sanction and helping to transmit it from generation to generation. So it is possible to conclude here that the election of the deacons conducted in the bible can become a useful electoral substratum on which to grow the Nigerian electoral system and also provide the moral principles necessary for the integration of the people of the country. Thus, the political class and the ruling elites in Nigeria must imbibe beliefs and attitudes of the Apostles to grow integration and cooperation. This must have sprang from their religious beliefs be they Christians, Muslims or African Traditional worshippers. This is because every religion has before our time, successfully maintained moral life in the society.

Beside the above, the problem identified with politics: the vulnerability of those playing it to show less reception to values that are relevant and beneficial to public good; and since religion assumes the position of helping in redeeming the Nigerian society and influence on the social and moral aspects of the people, this paper stands the chance of furnishing the politicians with insights that make them to be conscious of the sinfulness of their preoccupation with self and their cronyism attitude in political and electoral matters. To the unhappy, the suffering, the bereaved and the rest of the masses, when our leaders decide to do the right thing or rule according to laid down rules on national and electoral matters, let us follow them even when we are aggrieved to come out successful as the brethren including the murmuring group (Hellenists) did and they were able to succeed in electing the seven deacons who handled their challenges better. Overcoming our socio-political and democratic (electoral matters) challenges will not only integrate us but provide other countries of the world with stable political systems and a universal brotherhood of humans.

Endnotes

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